

Role of agricultural pesticides in India

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13150984>

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Abstract

Agricultural growth is the primary emphasis of Indian planning and policy. Pesticides have evolved into an essential tool for enhancing food production by acting as a plant protection agent. Pesticides also assist in preventing several deadly illnesses. Pesticide exposure, both occupational and environmental, causes a variety of human health issues. Chemical treatment remains the most frequent method for managing insect populations. They have an essential function in agriculture as plant protection agents, which assist in preventing crop losses. Pests cause tremendous costs in undeveloped nations due to their heavy load. Pesticides are a valuable ingredient that significantly boosts agricultural profitability. Pesticides improve productivity but pose a danger to food quality, the environment, and human health. Pesticides can harm the ecosystem, groundwater, and other bodies of water when they are applied. To mitigate the effects of toxic pesticides, additional measures such as bio-pesticides, botanicals, genetically modified crops, and other cultural practices should be used.

Keywords: Bio-pesticides, Chemical treatment, pesticides, etc.

Introduction

Pesticides are natural or manufactured substances used to manage pests, weeds, and diseases in plants in several agricultural applications. Pesticides include herbicides, insecticides, fungicides, rodenticides, and nematodes, among others. Insect pests generate considerable agricultural losses in both developing and industrialized nations. Reduced crop loss will be crucial, and enhanced pest management, including disease and weed control, will need significant effort. Pesticides have evolved as an important tool for plant protection and crop improvement throughout the agricultural development cycle.

Reviews

1. Dr. Sachin Kumar (2013) ^[5] Use of pesticides in agriculture and livestock animals and its impact on the environment of India The findings on the prevalence of pesticide residues in animal products made in India are fragmented, but they demonstrate that Indian consumers are exposed to these pesticides through their diet. Thus, heavy pesticide application has various

negative impacts on the environment and human health that cannot be disregarded.

2. R. K. Kole, K. Roy¹, B. N. Panja, E. Sankarganesh¹ T. Mandal and R. E. Worede (2019) ^[4] Use of Pesticides in Agriculture and Emergence of Resistant Pests in this paper author analysis that The level of pesticide, fungicide, and herbicide resistance in various pest species is also discussed. Understanding the elements that influence pest and resistance development is required for effective management techniques. The Insecticide Resistance Action Committee (IRAC), Fungicide Resistance Action Committee (FRAC), and Herbicide Resistance Action Committee (HRAC) all play essential roles in resistance management. Strategies for mitigating resistance development in conventional pesticides, the use of Plant Incorporated Protectants (PIPs) and biopesticides as alternatives to chemical pesticides, and some general guidelines are proposed for implementation.
3. Muhammad Jamil Khan, M.s. Qasim (2010) ^[3] Use of Pesticides and Their Role in Environmental Pollution

This article examines overall pesticide use in Pakistan in connection to pesticide costs, cotton, and rice support prices, pesticide use in various Pakistani provinces on different crops, and their influence on agricultural production. The environmental damage caused by pesticide usage, poisoning of soil and water resources, and the dangers involved with the disposal of empty containers are all explored in length.

4. Anamika Rana, and Nidhi Sharma (2022) ^[1] Heavy Uses of Pesticides in India: A Quantitative Analysis In this review, the author attempts to analyse and develop a complete picture of the -1 -1 excessive use of pesticides in several Indian states, as well as their harmful effects on the human body, water, and the environment. India is an agricultural country. The usage of agricultural pesticides has risen dramatically throughout the years. Maharashtra (13243 tonnes) and Uttar Pradesh (11557 tonnes) will use the most pesticides in 2020-21, while Punjab (5193 tonnes) and Haryana (4050 tonnes) would use fewer pesticides than the previous year. The states of Punjab, Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Haryana, and Andhra Pradesh used 70% of all pesticides. Excessive pesticide use is detrimental to humans, animals, and plants.
5. S. Selvaraj, B. Basavaraj1 and N.S. Hebsur (2014) ^[6] Pesticides use and their residuals in soil grains and

water of paddy ecosystem-A review Rice is one of India's key staple food crops, growing in various agro-climatic zones and covering an area of 14.5 lakh acres. The phrase 'rice is life' is particularly applicable to India, as this grain is critical to the country's food security and provides a living for millions of rural families. Rice is usually infested with pests during cultivation. Thus, farmers who cultivate rice employ pesticides to preserve their crops, some of which are persistent and pollute the soil. The vast field investigation revealed that insecticides were utilised in huge quantities. Pesticides are often used to crop fields to battle insect pests and increase rice yield.

Objectives

1. To Examine the State-Wise Consumption of Chemical Pesticides in India
2. To Understand the Commodity-Wise Consumption of Chemical Pesticides & Bio-Pesticides.

Materilas and Methods

The present study is based on secondary data from various articles, government agencies for policy support, journals, websites, thesis, books, and annual reports from India and Karnataka.

Table 1: To Examine the State-Wise Consumption of Chemical Pesticides in India

S. No.	States/UTs	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23
1	Andhra Pradesh	1689	1559	1559	1759	2001
2	Bihar	850	850	995	850	995
3	Chhattisgarh	1770	1672	1639	1740	1775
4	Goa	25	30	30	32	34
5	Gujarat	1608	1784	1573	1869	1750
6	Haryana	4015	4200	4050	4066	4066
7	Himachal Pradesh	322	881	56	279	470
8	Jharkhand	646	681	1161	450	450
9	Karnataka	1524	1568	1930	2224	1669
10	Kerala	995	656	585	532	504
11	Madhya Pradesh	540	540	691	654	598
12	Maharashtra	11746	12783	13243	13175	6814
13	Orissa	1609	1115	1158	1240	1348
14	Punjab	5543	4995	5193	5376	5130
15	Rajasthan	2290	2088	2330	2104	1865
16	Tamil Nadu	1901	2225	1834	1851	1952
17	Telangana	4894	4915	4986	4920	4920
18	Uttar Pradesh	11049	12217	11557	11688	11824
19	Uttarakhand	195	224	135	213	111
20	West Bengal	3190	3630	3630	3630	3321
Sub Total		56402	58613	58336	58653	51597
North-Eastern						
21	Arunachal Pradesh	5	5	2	1.4	NR
22	Assam	256	410	420	474	455
23	Manipur	NR	25	46	NR	NR
24	Meghalaya	Organic State	Organic State	Organic State	Organic State	Organic State
25	Mizoram	26	27	NR	29	31
26	Nagaland	21	19	36	41	NR
27	Sikkim	Organic State	Organic State	Organic State	Organic State	Organic State
28	Tripura	349	364	NR	NR	NR
Sub Total		657	851	503	545	485
Union Territories						
29	Andaman & Nicobar	NR	NR	1	NR	NR
30	Chandigarh	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR
31	Dadra & Nagar Haveli & Daman & Diu	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR

32	Delhi	110	NR	NR	NR	NR
33	Jammu & Kashmir	2459	2198	3352	4086	384
34	Ladakh	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR
35	Lakshadweep	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR
36	Pondicherry	42	40	NR	NR	NR
Sub Total		2611	2238	3353	4086	384
Grand Total		59670	61702	62193	63284	52466

Source: States / UTs Zonal Conference on Inputs (Plant Protection) for Rabi and Kharif Seasons

Fig 1: Shows data on chemical pesticide consumption by state from 2018-19 to 2022-23. Here's a study of the data. Overall Trend: The use of chemical pesticides fluctuates over time, with a slight decrease from 2019-20 to 2022-23

This table shows data on chemical pesticide consumption by state from 2018-19 to 2022-23. Here's a study of the data. Overall Trend: The use of chemical pesticides fluctuates over time, with a slight decrease from 2019-20 to 2022-23. States with the highest consumption: Maharashtra consistently has the highest use of chemical pesticides among all states. Other states with heavy usage include Uttar Pradesh, Punjab, Gujarat, and Telangana. Regional Patterns: Northern states, such as Punjab, Haryana, and Uttar Pradesh, have relatively high consumption levels, which are most likely due to intensive farming practices in these areas. Southern states like Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, and Tamil Nadu also have high consumption rates, demonstrating the importance of agriculture in these regions. Trends in certain states: Some states' consumption rates change over time. For example, Maharashtra's consumption falls dramatically between 2018-19 and 2022-

23. Haryana's consumption has been mostly stable throughout the years. States such as Gujarat and Karnataka have shown fluctuations, but with a slight decreasing trend in recent years. Data Quality: In certain circumstances, "NR" (Not Reported) denotes missing data. This may have an influence on the overall analysis, especially in states with irregular data reporting. Yearly variations: While consumption differs by state, the overall trend shows a slight decrease in total consumption between 2019-20 and 2022-23. Finally, this data analysis gives insight on the distribution and patterns of chemical pesticide use throughout India's states. It emphasises the need of pesticide monitoring for sustainable agricultural practices and environmental protection. Addressing missing data and supporting alternative pest management strategies may help enhance analytical and decision-making processes.

Table 2: Commodity-Wise Consumption of Chemical Pesticides & Bio-Pesticides

Year	Pesticides	Crops									Grand Total
		Cereal	Vegetable	Pulse	Oilseed	Fruit	Plantation	Cash Crop	Fibre	Other	
2018-19	Chemical	17270	3845	5759	4881	2449	432	4995	3567	1055	44253
	Bio Pesticides	808	575	664	909	304	122	282	39	48	3751
	Total	18078	4420	6424	5790	2752	554	5277	3607	1103	48004
2019-20	Chemical	14937	3870	4390	4565	2242	310	4832	4281	861	40288
	Bio Pesticides	982	488	317	827	180	144	207	329	199	3673
	Total	15919	4359	4707	5392	2422	454	5039	4610	1060	43962
2020-21	Chemical	17149	4773	4567	4723	1665	338	6090	4006	1388	44700
	Bio Pesticides	1285	775	768	984	149	137	559	83	669	5409
	Total	18435	5548	5335	5708	1814	475	6649	4089	2057	50109
2021-22	Chemical	19385	4578	6062	4875	2163	301	5865	3436	995	47660
	Bio Pesticides	1390	693	373	747	153	238	491	42	85	4212
	Total	20774	5271	6435	5622	2317	538	6356	3478	1080	51872
2022-23	Chemical	17179	3997	3766	3024	1812	219	6368	1899	3529	41795
	Bio Pesticides	1251	505	312	159	220	102	466	73	1900	4986
	Total	18430	4502	4078	3183	2032	321	6834	1972	5430	46782

Source: States / UTs Zonal Conference on Inputs (Plant Protection) for Rabi and Kharif Seasons

Fig 2: Pesticide intake, both chemical and bio-pesticide, appears to be rather stable over time, with an overall trend of increasing total consumption

Agricultural practices and environmental protection. Addressing missing data and supporting alternative pest management strategies may help enhance analytical and decision-making processes.

Overall Trend: Pesticide intake, both chemical and bio-pesticide, appears to be rather stable over time, with an overall trend of increasing total consumption. Pesticide use in 2022-23 is somewhat lower than the previous year, suggesting a shift in pesticide usage trends or other factors influencing consumption. Chemical pesticides: Chemical pesticide use has historically been far higher than that of bio-pesticides. There is a noticeable variance in use across distinct years and crops, but overall, chemical pesticide usage has increased somewhat over time. Bio-Pesticides: Bio-pesticide use is far lower than that of chemical pesticides, but it has been expanding in recent years. Bio-pesticide application varies by crop and year. Yearly

Comparison: When comparing year-to-year data, there are differences in the usage of chemical and bio-pesticides among crops. Some years see increased consumption, while others experience a decrease, which might be due to a variety of factors such as changes in agricultural practices, bug outbreaks, weather conditions, or the use of alternative pest management tactics. Bio-Pesticide Use: Bio-pesticide use looks to be steadily growing over time, indicating a potential shift towards more environmentally friendly and sustainable pest control practices. Data Source and Reliability: The data source is "States/UTs Zonal Conferences on Plant Protection Inputs for Kharif & Rabi Seasons," suggesting that the information was acquired via conferences conducted by states and union territories. It's worth mentioning that just 17 states supplied data for 2022-23, which might affect the data's overall representativeness. Finally, the study of this table demonstrates patterns in the

usage of chemical pesticides and bio-pesticides across diverse crops over five years, indicating potential shifts towards more sustainable pest management methods.

Findings and Suggestions

1. Chemical pesticides have dangerous elements that are likely to contaminate the land, water, and atmosphere.
2. These not only harm the target creatures, but they can also kill non-targeted organisms.
3. When humans and animals are exposed to these, they develop illnesses, diseases, allergies, and respiratory issues.
4. When they are scattered over agricultural fields, they can contaminate growing crops, making them toxic and unsuitable for ingestion.

Conclusions

Pesticides have been used in India for over 60 years to manage weeds and insects in agriculture, public health, and other areas. They are quick, easy, and cost-effective. It has been demonstrated that herbicides have contributed significantly to raising agricultural productivity and farmers' incomes worldwide. India is a self-sufficient producer and exporter of pesticides. Some concerns require immediate action to enhance the domestic pesticide sector and ensure the safe use of pesticides. First and foremost, it is critical to regulate and promote the use of low-cost, ecologically friendly pesticides. Uniformity in testing processes and the deregistration of old, harmful pesticides are required to avoid negative consequences. The systems for ensuring quality at the point of sale and protecting farmers against counterfeit products must be enhanced. The industrial association may also be involved in this duty. The second crucial factor is to promote safe application procedures and raise farmer knowledge.

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